

Anti-fouling plasma treated membranes with stable superhydrophobic properties for membrane distillation

Dimosthenis Ioannou^{a,b}, Prexa Shah^c, Kosmas Ellinas^{a,d}, Michael Kappl^c, Andreas Sapalidis^a, Hans-Jürgen Butt^c and Evangelos Gogolides^{*a}

^aInstitute of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology, NCSR “Demokritos”, Aghia Paraskevi, 15341, Attica, Greece

^bSchool of Mechanical Engineering, National Technical University of Athens, Zografou, 15780, Attica, Greece

^cMax Planck Institute for Polymer Research, Ackermannweg 10, Mainz, 55128, Germany

^dDepartment of food science and nutrition, School of the Environment, University of the Aegean, Ierou Lochou & Makrygianni St, 81400, Myrina, Lemnos, Greece

*e-mail: e.gogolides@inn.demokritos.gr

ABSTRACT

Long-lasting, superhydrophobic membranes are considered the holy grail for desalination. Such membranes are expected to exhibit stable performance and improved anti-fouling properties. Herein, we present superhydrophobic Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) and Cellulose acetate (CA) membranes, modified using plasma micro-nanotexturing followed by plasma deposition, which demonstrate enhanced anti-fouling properties in two modes of membrane distillation (MD), air gap (AGMD) and direct contact (DCMD). The plasma-treated PTFE membranes (initially hydrophobic) exhibit stable performance, with constant fluxes of 3.3 L/m²h in AGMD and 8.5 L/m²h in DCMD, excellent salt rejection (> 99.9 %) and robust fouling resistance during long-

hour operations and very high bovine serum albumin (BSA) concentrations (3 g/L). The same observation is made for the plasma-treated CA membranes (initially hydrophilic) which demonstrate flux values of 3.9 L/m²h in AGMD and 9.3 L/m²h in DCMD. Going one step further, we introduce a novel method to study the stability of the superhydrophobic state, by monitoring the membrane surface *in situ* during MD, using white light reflectance spectroscopy (WLRS). As revealed by the unaffected reflectance spectrum, no wetting transition occurs for the plasma-treated PTFE membrane for liquids with surface tension as low as 39.1 mN/m, whereas wetting transition is observed for the pristine PTFE when surface tension decreases below 60 mN/m.

Keywords: membrane distillation, plasma nanotexturing, superhydrophobic membranes, anti-fouling, biofouling

1. Introduction

As water demands are rising, both in industry and society due to overpopulation, alternative methods for clean water production are essential for the containment of water scarcity. Membrane Distillation (MD) is a low-cost, energy saving and promising process that is being investigated as a complementary solution for the treatment of challenging feedwaters, since lower temperatures and pressures than traditional distillation are required. Although new techniques have been proposed for atmospheric water collection, using specially designed interfaces,¹⁻³ membrane distillation is still the leading technique due to its widespread application. During MD, a porous and hydrophobic membrane, that is in contact with a hot feed solution, allows only hot water vapor to pass through the pores and condense on the other side.⁴

Therefore it is essential to prevent mass transfer of liquids as they might contain salts, oils and foulants that could contaminate the distillate.⁵

The accumulation of undesirable material on solid surfaces that affects their properties and performance, is generally referred to as fouling.⁶ It can refer to biological, organic and inorganic material. When biological entities, commonly found in seawater, adsorb onto the membrane surface, and subsequently form a layer that blocks the pores and reduces permeate flux, in the world of MD this phenomenon is known as bio-fouling. It first starts as a monolayer, where dissolved and colloidal organics deposit onto the surface and form a conditioning film to which bacteria adhere.⁷ This gradually results in the attachment of larger molecules, like proteins, to finally form a robust and continuous bio-film.⁸⁻¹¹ It is, therefore, evident that distilled water flux reduction, due to pore clogging, or reduction of the permeate quality, due to pore wetting, are important drawbacks in MD.

To address these limitations, superhydrophobicity has recently become a requirement in membrane fabrication.^{6,12,21-30,13,31-33,14-20} Examples of such membranes exist in literature, *i.e.* Liao *et al.*³⁰ reported a superhydrophobic membrane (SWCA 170 °) by merging a surface layer fabricated by electrospraying a PVDF/PDMS/silica fume blended solution and an electrospun nanofibrous poly(vinylidene fluoride) PVDF support. Even though superhydrophobicity was achieved, permeate flux started to decline after 6 – 10 hours when a NaCl/HA or a NaCl/ TDAB solution was used. In another effort, Warsinger *et al.*¹⁴ also achieved superhydrophobicity by using initiated chemical vapor deposition (iCVD) of perfluorodecyl acrylate (PFDA) on PVDF membranes and tested their anti-fouling properties on a static MD setup. Their study showed that the air layer formed on the surface of submerged superhydrophobic membranes reduces biological fouling but had the opposite effect on scaling. Nthunya *et al.*^{31,34} synthesized PVDF

nanofiber membranes embedded with silanized silica nanoparticles, coated with a hydrophilic active layer containing silver nanoparticles and carboxylated multi-walled carbon nanotubes. The samples were tested in DCMD and, even though they performed better than pristine membranes, flux decreased by 15 % during the 50-hour operation. A polypropylene (PP) composite membrane featuring a coating of SiO₂ nanoparticles and a fluorinated modification was fabricated by Shao *et al.*,¹⁶ which performed better than pristine samples when used in Vacuum MD (VMD) against a 15 wt% NaCl, 9 wt% MgCl₂ feed solution. Still, flux was lower than pristine samples in standard desalination. Superhydrophobic PVDF microporous membranes with micro-nano hierarchical structures were prepared from Sun *et al.* by combining immersion precipitation with rolling embossing²¹ and showed a good anti-fouling performance in a 100 h VMD process. While salt rejection was 99.99 %, again permeate flux declined with time. Ray *et al.*³⁵ modified a PVDF membrane using trichloro(1H,1H,2H,2H-perfluorooctyl)silane (TPFOS) and titanium dioxide nanoparticles (TiO₂-NPs) as chemical modifiers to render it superhydrophobic. When tested in MD for anti-fouling performance evaluation, flux remained stable, still the reported operation lasted only for 180 min. This brief literature review suggests that flux reduction is very common in reported works related to superhydrophobic membranes, as a sign of either biofilm formation^{23,27,36,37} or scaling.²⁶

Other efforts towards the fabrication of antifouling membranes include plasma processing, which is mostly employed for surface chemistry functionalization. In that sense, it is commonly used for hydrophilic groups creation like OH, COOH, CO^{35,38} or plasma deposition of a hydrophobic polymer on the membrane surface.^{39,40} Even though flux and porosity increase, as well as high water contact angles were reported, none of these methods achieved superhydrophobicity on initially hydrophilic membranes, neither do they induce changes in the surface morphology of

membranes. On top of that, wetting transitions on membranes during MD operation are indirectly assumed when the distillate conductivity increases (*i.e.* salt rejection and distillate purity decrease) and very few real-time monitoring methods have been proposed.^{41,42}

We have extensively worked on transforming rigid polymeric substrates to superhydrophobic,^{43–45} and we have reported that superhydrophobic surfaces fabricated using our methodology, which involves plasma treatment, can repel bacteria containing solutions in static mode for more than 72 hours,⁴⁶ while sustaining superhydrophobicity underwater for several days.⁴⁷ Recently, we have demonstrated that it is possible to render commercial membranes to superhydrophobic, regardless of their initial wetting properties, featuring enhanced performance in MD and exhibiting superior anti-wetting properties when common surfactant sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) was introduced in the saline feed solution.⁴⁸

Herein, we demonstrate the long-lasting, anti-fouling properties of superhydrophobic and plasma treated PTFE and CA membranes in continuous flow conditions, using a high concentration (up to 3 g/L) of bovine serum albumin (BSA) in the saline feed solution. Using our plasma technology, we alter membrane surface morphology and chemistry at will through a combination of plasma etching and plasma deposition that results in superhydrophobicity. In this work, the anti-fouling evaluation is performed in the two most common modes of membrane distillation, air-gap and direct contact (AGMD and DCMD). We also address the gap of real time monitoring of superhydrophobicity under flow conditions and introduce White Light Reflectance Spectroscopy (WLRS) as a novel method for in-situ monitoring the superhydrophobic state during MD. Using this method, we showcase the stability of our plasma treated membranes, compared to commercial ones, by lowering the surface tension of the saline feed solution with the gradual addition of SDS. Untreated PTFE membrane's wetting properties fade, as indicated

by reflectance decrease, for a liquid with surface tension of 55 mN/m (0.01mM of SDS), whereas the plasma treated PTFE membrane exhibits stable superhydrophobicity, as revealed by the practically unaffected reflectance spectrum, for liquids of surface tension down to 39.1 mN/m, corresponding to 10 times higher SDS concentration (0.1mM). Finally, in terms of MD performance, no flux decrease over a course of 50 hours was observed for the plasma treated PTFE membrane (in both modes of distillation), even when a very high BSA concentration (3 g/L) was used, making this an achievement against biofouling rarely reported in literature. Up to now, typical BSA concentrations vary from several mg/L up to 1 g/L.^{23,27,49-51} The superhydrophobic CA membrane also exhibited excellent anti-fouling properties after plasma treatment by producing the highest flux both in AGMD and in DCMD and very high salt rejection (> 99.99 %). Moreover, no biofilm was observed in any of the superhydrophobic membranes after the anti-fouling test, whereas in the case of pristine membranes the surface was completely covered.

2. Experimental Section

2.1 Membrane materials

Flat sheet, hydrophobic polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) membranes were kindly provided by Donaldson (<https://www.donaldson.com>), featuring mean pore size of 0.2 μm . These membranes consist of a 30 μm thick top layer featuring a mesh of 50 nm thick PTFE fibers and a 120 μm polypropylene (PP) substrate featuring thicker fibers (30 μm in diameter). Hydrophilic, cellulose acetate (CA) membrane disks of 142 mm diameter with a mean pore size of 0.22 μm and an average thickness of 90 μm were supplied by Dorsan (<https://www.dorsanfiltration.com>). They

consist of two layers, 30 μm thick each, featuring a mesh of thin fibers and an inner layer between them featuring thicker fibers for mechanical stability.

2.2 Plasma treatment of membranes

For the texturing of all membranes an Alcatel Reactive Ion Etcher (RIE) NE330 was used, with 400 W plasma power, 10 mTorr pressure and 100 sccm flow rate of O_2 . The process and the roughness creation mechanism has been reported for various polymeric materials and in various plasma reactors, and is extremely reproducible.^{43,44,52-55} PTFE samples were treated for 3 min on their top side and CA membranes were textured for 1 minute on each side. The plasma deposition process was performed in the MET system of Adixen, a high-density Inductively Coupled Plasma (ICP) reactor, outfitted with a helicon source (at 13.56 MHz), where octafluorocyclobutane (C_4F_8) plasma was utilized. The process parameters were: 900 W plasma power, 5.33 Pa pressure, 25 sccm C_4F_8 flow rate, 0 W bias, 0 $^\circ\text{C}$ electrode temperature, 1 min 20 sec duration on both sides for the PTFE membranes, and 4 min on both sides for the CA membranes. Detailed description of the plasma treatment of membranes can be found in our previous publication.⁴⁸

Figure 1. Schematics of plasma-treated and untreated flat sheet membranes, as well as images showing the respective water contact angles, are shown. The plasma treatment includes two steps: one that produces surface roughness and a second one that lowers the surface energy— O_2 etching and C_4F_8 deposition.

2.3 Membrane characterization

Detailed description of the membrane characterization methods can be found in our previous publication.⁴⁸ Our methods include: scanning electron microscopy (SEM) for the morphological characterization, water static contact angle (WSCA) and contact angle hysteresis (CAH) for the wetting properties evaluation, liquid surface tension, liquid entry pressure (LEP), porosity as well as tortuosity measurements.

2.4 Membrane Distillation Setups

A lab-scale setup for Direct Contact Membrane Distillation (DCMD) was established to test the performance of plasma treated membranes (Figure 2). The tested membrane is mounted in a module made of Acetal, featuring an effective area of 27.5 cm². The DCMD setup consists of the electronic equipment for the control and measurement of liquid flows at both sides of the membrane. The feed system consists of polypropylene water tank, a pump (ENM 25S Tellarini pompe) and an electronic mass flow meter. A constant flow of 100 ml/min of hot saline water is maintained to the feed side of the membrane. A similar system drives the cold-water stream to the other side at a constant flow rate of 100 ml/min. The temperatures of the feed and permeate streams are regulated *via* plate type heat exchangers and heating / cooling circulation baths. The permeate water flow is measured with an electronic mass flow meter, while the salinity of both flows is detected with two conductivity meters.⁵⁶ For standard distillation, the feed solution contained 30 g/L NaCl and the desalination duration was 3 hours. For the bio-fouling evaluation, 1000 mg/L of Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA) was added to the feed saline solution every 60 minutes, while keeping its temperature constant at 53 °C (exceeding this temperature could lead to protein coagulation), and 15 °C for the cold-water flow. The duration of each experiment was 3 hours, therefore after the 1st hour the BSA concentration was increased to 2 g/L, and after the 2nd hour it was 3 g/L. MD operating conditions are presented in Table I.

The lab-scale Air Gap Membrane Distillation (AGMD) setup is described in detail in our previous publication (Figure 2B).⁴⁸ For standard distillation, the feed solution contained 30 g/L NaCl and the desalination duration was 1 hour. For the bio-fouling evaluation, 1000 mg/L of Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA) was added to the feed saline solution, while keeping its temperature at 53 °C (exceeding this temperature could lead to protein coagulation) and 15 °C

for the cold-water flow. Desalination duration in AGMD was 50-70 hours. Operating conditions are presented in Table I.

Figure 2. Direct Contact Membrane Distillation (DCMD) setup schematic (A) and Air Gap Membrane Distillation (AGMD) setup schematic (B).

Table I. Operating parameters for DCMD and AGMD tests

Variables	Values	
	DCMD	AGMD
Feed inlet temperature	53 °C	53 °C
Feed flow rate	0.1 L/min	1 L/min
Feed pressure	~0.1 bar	~0.2 bar
Coolant temperature	15 °C	15 °C
Coolant flow rate	0.1 L/min	2 L/min
Air gap width	-	3.5 mm
Effective membrane area	27.5 cm ²	38 cm ²
Concentration of NaCl	0.59 M	0.59 M
Concentration of BSA	0.015 / 0.030 / 0.45 mM	0.0015 mM
Feed conductivity @ 22 °C	54 mS/cm	54 mS/cm
Feed surface tension @ 22 °C	60 ± 5 mN/m	60 ± 5 mN/m
Test duration	3 h	50-70 h

2.5 White Light Reflectance Spectrometry (WLRS) measurements

For the real-time monitoring of a membrane's surface during MD operation, a complementary DCMD module was fabricated to allow WLRS measurements (Figure 3). The setup consists of: a broad-band deuterium/tungsten UV-VIS-NIR light source, a PC-driven spectrometer (Ocean

Optics QE65000-ABS), a fiber optic reflection probe (6 + 1 fibers) from Ocean Optics operating in the corresponding spectral range, two peristaltic pumps, a hot plate and the module where the probe and the membrane are mounted. The bandwidth of 300 nm to 500 nm is monitored, since in that area of the spectrum the absorbance of all liquids used is zero, therefore any changes in reflectance that occur are only related to changes in the wetting state. More details on the WLRS method can be found in our previously published work.⁴⁷ In short, the working principle of the method is the following: when an air layer exists between the membrane and the supernatant liquid, reflectance values are higher, when wetting occurs the air layer diminishes and reflectance gradually decreases.

Before testing the membranes in MD, they were submerged inside a petri dish and their properties were evaluated in static mode. Then, their superhydrophobic state stability was tested *in situ* during MD using feed temperature of 60 °C, pure water flow temperature of 20 °C and flows of 9 ml/min and 3ml/min respectively. Initially, a standard saline solution of 0.59 M NaCl concentration was used and, using a syringe pump, a Sodium Dodecyl Sulfate (SDS) saline solution was gradually added to the feed water tank to decrease surface tension from 72.8 mN/m down to 39.1 mN/m, with the final SDS concentration being 0.1mM. The duration of each step, shown in Figure 3, was 10 minutes. The total duration of each test, static and MD mode, was 1 hour. To achieve total wetting in all membranes, lower surface tension values were required, thus the feed solution was replaced with isopropanol (22.3 mN/m).

(A)

(B)

Figure 3. MD module that enables WLRS monitoring during operation (A). Schematic of WLRS method for monitoring membrane surfaces submerged in liquids with the corresponding reflectance spectra. When an air layer is maintained between the membrane and the supernatant liquid reflectance is high and when a membrane is wet, the air layer diminishes and reflectance drops (B).

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Membrane Characterization

In the scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of Figure 4, surface topography before and after plasma treatment are shown. Hierarchical structures, by means of peaks and valleys in the micro and nano scale, are obtained after O₂ plasma etching on both PTFE and CA membranes. The height of these structures, as well as the mean distance between them (it would not be inaccurate to use the term “pore size” for this surface characteristic), increase according to plasma duration. Because of the high surface-air fraction caused by this rough topography, which we refer to as micro-nanotexturing, membrane surfaces are resistant to wetting and the liquid air interface grows, favoring mass transfer.^{51,52}

Deionized (DI) water was used to quantify the water static contact angle (WSCA) and contact angle hysteresis (CAH). Since only the top side was treated with the combination of O₂ nanotexturing and C₄F₈ plasma deposition, the plasma-treated PTFE membranes were superhydrophobic only on the topside. On the other hand, since CA membranes were treated on both sides, they were superhydrophobic with WSCAs above 160° and CAHs below 10° on both sides. Pristine membranes were simply hydrophobic in the case of PTFE and hydrophilic in the case of CA (which is why untreated CA is not present in Figure 4G). By using liquids of lower surface tension, the WSCA of all plasma treated membranes did not decrease below 150°, even for surface tension of 45mN/m, and remained 140° when surface tension dropped below these values. CAH stayed below 10° down to 55 mN/m and remained below 20° even down to 45 mN/m. This indicates that plasma treated membranes become sticky but still liquid repellent at

that point. The WSCA of untreated PTFE membranes were measured below 140° for all liquids above 45 mN/m , and further decreased for liquids of lower surface tension.

Figure 4. Top-down SEM images of pristine PTFE membrane (A), after 2 min (B) and after 4 min (C) of texturing in O_2 plasma. Top-down SEM images of pristine CA membrane (D), after 2min (E) and after 4 min (F) of texturing in O_2 plasma. (G) Water static contact angle and contact angle hysteresis of the top side of plasma treated and untreated membranes as a function of surface tension along with the lines for the superhydrophobicity requirements at 150° (contact angle) and at 10° (hysteresis). (H) LEP and maximum pore radius for each membrane type.

All membrane LEP values were measured above 1 bar(g), which is considered a critical point, as indicated on Figure 4H. Since the O₂ etching process is a pore-widening technique, LEP decreases for all membranes that have undergone plasma treatment in comparison to untreated samples. PTFE features the maximum value of 5.5 bar, and following plasma treatment this value is reduced by 13%. LEP of the plasma treated CA membrane was measured at 1.8 bar, which is still above the critical point; fact that further proves the capabilities of our technology regardless of the initial wetting properties of membranes.

An increase in porosity was measured for all plasma treated samples. Since O₂ plasma is a surface modification and functionalization technique, we can safely assume that the inner layers maintain their structural integrity and this increase in porosity is mostly due to surface alternations. In the case of PTFE membranes, porosity increased by 3 % after plasma treatment, from 59 to 62 %, while for the CA membranes, initial value is much higher at 77 % (untreated) and reaches 81 % after plasma treatment, which can explain the fact that these membranes yield higher flux in MD. More information on porosity, tortuosity and average pore size of these membranes can be found in our previous publication.⁴⁸

3.2 AGMD anti-fouling performance

We have already reported the performance of plasma treated membranes in AGMD using a 60 °C temperature difference (75 - 15 °C) during a 48-hour experiment duration.⁴⁸ Plasma treated membranes not only featured a 10 % higher flux compared to pristine samples, but also demonstrated a stable performance. To evaluate their anti-fouling performance, 1 g/L of BSA was added to the standard saline feed solution (0.59 M NaCl) and the temperatures used are 53 °C for the feed and 15 °C for the cool flow. The fouling and the antifouling mechanisms during

AGMD are illustrated in Figure 5. In the case of untreated PTFE, flux was measured at 2.6 L/m²h in the beginning, while in the end of the experiment it decreased at 2.4 L/m²h, as shown in Figure 5. This issue was not observed when using the corresponding plasma treated membrane. Indeed, flux was 3.2 L/m²h for the plasma treated PTFE and remained stable during 50 hours of operation. As for the plasma treated CA membrane, flux is measured at 4 L/m²h in the beginning of the experiment and, even if a decrease was observed, flux is still the highest at 3.6 L/m²h at the end of the 50-hour long test. Salt rejection is excellent and higher than 99.9 % for all membranes.

These results indicate that plasma induced superhydrophobicity is very effective, since the air layer that is formed between the surface structures prevents wetting during MD, as demonstrated by the stable performances and the excellent salt rejection rates. Subsequently, this air layer also prevents the adsorption of proteins by not allowing liquid to make contact with the pore mouths. Therefore, no attractive interactions between the protein and the membrane material occur, as proven by the constant flux values, at least on the plasma treated PTFE membrane.

Figure 5. (a) Anti-fouling performance of untreated and plasma treated membranes in AGMD. A 3.5 wt% sodium chloride solution with 1 g/L BSA concentration was used as feed. The feed and distillate temperatures were 53°C and 15°C, respectively. Schematic of fouling mechanism on pristine membranes (b) and anti-fouling mechanism of superhydrophobic membranes (c).

3.3 DCMD anti-fouling performance

The results of the anti-fouling tests in DCMD are shown in Figure 6. Since this MD method usually features increased mass transfer due to the smaller distance water vapor travels before it is condensed and collected, fluxes for all membranes are measured higher compared to AGMD. The temperatures used for the feed and clean water flows were the same as in the previous section (53 – 15 °C). However, in this test the BSA concentration was not constant, 1 g/L was added every 60 minutes, so at the end of the 3 hour long experiment the saline feed solution would include 3 g/L of BSA. Just like in the previous section, flux decrease was observed for the untreated PTFE membrane. In the beginning of the experiment, flux was 7 L/m²h and by the end it was 4.5 L/m²h, decreased by 30 %. On the contrary no substantial flux decrease was measured for the plasma treated PTFE membrane, stable flux was measured at 8.5 L/m²h and permeate conductivity was less than 10 µS/cm, thus rendering salt rejection excellent at 99.95 %, despite the high concentration of BSA. In the case of the plasma treated CA membrane, initial flux in this test was measured at 9.3 L/m²h, and the gradual addition of BSA in the feed solution had a small effect in its performance. After the first hour flux was 9.5 L/m²h, but after the second hour corresponding to 2 g/L of BSA, it was slightly reduced at 9 L/m²h. Finally, by the end of the third hour, corresponding to 3 g/L of BSA, it was measured at 8.4 L/m²h; a total decrease of 10 %. Salt rejection was once again excellent and higher than 99.9 %.

Figure 6. Anti-fouling performance of untreated and plasma treated membranes at different BSA concentrations in DCMD with SEM images of their surfaces after the test, for comparison, plasma treated CA (A), plasma treated PTFE (B) and untreated PTFE (C). Notice the flux reduction correlation with the biofilm formation in the case of untreated PTFE membrane. A 3.5 wt% sodium chloride solution with varying BSA concentration (1, 2 and 3 g/L) was used as feed. The feed and distillate temperatures were 53°C and 15°C respectively.

We attribute the flux decrease of the untreated samples to the gradual formation of a thick and robust biofilm on their surfaces. Attractive interactions between the membrane material and BSA are responsible for partially clogging the pores by means of small protein nucleation spots. These spots play a crucial part in bio-film formation since they ignite the creation of a monolayer of deposited proteins, which subsequently thickens and widens with time. Flux decrease was observed, in both AGMD and DCMD, and biofilm is clearly visible on the surface from the SEM images in Figure 6C (taken after the antifouling experiments in DCMD).

Notably, none of these occurred on the superhydrophobic plasma treated PTFE and CA membranes. As shown by the top-down SEM images in Figure 6A&B, no biofilm is present. Only some inconsistent and sporadic formations are visible which derive from the protein residue that is left on the surfaces after water evaporates, leaving the texturing induced by plasma evidently unaffected. The excellent performance against this highly concentrated BSA feed solution is ascribed to robust superhydrophobicity and the successful coating of the inner pore layers during the plasma deposition process. Additionally, WSCAs and CAHs were measured after the anti-fouling experiments, and all plasma treated membranes still met the criteria of superhydrophobicity with WSCAs higher than 160° and CAHs around 10° , a fact which further proves the durability of the structures and the coating obtained through our plasma technology.

3.4 Stability of membranes' superhydrophobic properties

We first measured reflectance, by applying our WLRS method, on static conditions (Figure 7A&B) using an untreated and a plasma treated PTFE membrane, inside a petri dish submerged in water containing 0.59 M of NaCl (30 g/L). Then, with the addition of an SDS/NaCl aqueous solution, surface tension was gradually reduced from 72.8 mN/m to 39.1 mN/m, with the final SDS concentration being 0.1mM. Reflectance remains stable at 4 % (at 300 nm) in the case of superhydrophobic membrane, indicating stable superhydrophobicity. On the contrary, in the case of untreated PTFE membrane, a decrease in reflectance was observed. Reflectance at 300 nm had an initial value of 7 %, for surface tension of 72.8 mN/m, and by the end of the experiment it was measured at 5 %, while wetting transition initiated when surface tension reached 56.3 mN/m. In order to observe wetting on the plasma treated membrane, a solution of much lower surface

tension had to be used. Total wetting occurred with the introduction of isopropanol in the feed solution, when surface tension was reduced down to 22.3 mN/m.

Then, to study the superhydrophobic stability of our membranes in real time under MD conditions, we applied WLRS for monitoring the membrane surfaces during MD operation. Similarly, to what was observed in static mode, reflectance for the untreated membrane dropped, from 11 % (at 300 nm) to 9 %, but remained practically stable at 5.5 % (at 300 nm) for the plasma treated membrane (Figure 7C&D), indicating a stable superhydrophobic state even under flow conditions, for liquids of surface tension down to 39.1 mN/m. The wetting transition occurred at 56.3 mN/m for the untreated membrane, and it gradually developed from wetting of the pore mouths to partially wetted pores and eventually total wetting. Wetting transition was not observed in the case of the superhydrophobic plasma treated membranes which remained in the non-wetted state down to 39.1 mN/m (0.1mM of SDS), as indicated by the stable reflectance spectrum. Again, to observe total wetting, isopropanol had to be introduced on the feed side and reflectance reached the minimum value of 0.5 % at 300 nm when surface tension reached 22.3 mN/m. The generally lower reflectance values of the plasma treated membranes, compared to untreated, is attributed to plasma-induced surface roughness that weakens the intensity of the specularly reflected light detected by the probe.

Figure 7. Reflectance spectra of untreated PTFE membrane (A) and plasma treated PTFE (B) at static conditions for different surface tensions corresponding to different SDS concentrations in the feed saline solution. (C) and (D) are the same spectra during MD. Notice that reflectance decreases along with the lowering of surface tension on untreated membranes in both cases. On the contrary in the case of plasma treated membranes reflectance remains almost completely stable down to 39.1 mN/m. Insets: schematics of the wetting states and their corresponding reflectance spectra; for the untreated membrane partial wetting occurs at 56.3 mN/m and gradually advances to full wetting while the plasma treated remains non-wetted down to 39.1 mN/m.

4. Conclusions

In this work, we demonstrate the long lasting, anti-fouling properties of plasma treated, superhydrophobic membranes in both Air-Gap and Direct-Contact Membrane Distillation setups. Specifically, the plasma treated PTFE samples demonstrate impressive properties with stable performances and fluxes at 3.4 and 8.5 L/m²h on AGMD and DCMD respectively, excellent salt rejection rates (> 99.9 %) and robust anti-fouling resistances, not only during 50-hour operations, but also against very high BSA concentrations at 3 g/L. On the contrary, untreated PTFE samples not only show decreased flux compared to standard MD when the protein was added in the feed solution (see supporting information S1-2), but also flux further decreases over time. Additionally, plasma treated CA membranes, that were initially hydrophilic, demonstrate the highest flux values at 3.9 L/m²h on AGMD and 9.3 L/m²h on DCMD, with excellent anti-fouling properties. Furthermore, WLRS was employed as a novel technique to observe the superhydrophobic state stability during MD operation, using mixtures with low surface tension as feed to mimic real time conditions. The plasma treated membrane's superhydrophobic properties remained stable for liquids with surface tension down to 39.1 mN/m, while on the untreated PTFE membrane, wetting transition was observed in the early stages of the experiment, when a mixture of 56.3 mN/m was used.

Supporting Information

Standard AGMD performance

Standard DCMD performance

Absorbance spectra of SDS/aqueous solutions and isopropanol

Acknowledgments

Financial support has been provided by the Future and Emerging Technologies (FET) Horizon 2020 project [Harmonic](#). Financial support has also been provided by the Horizon 2022 EIC Transition Open project SuperClean.

References

- (1) Nioras, D.; Ellinas, K.; Gogolides, E. Atmospheric Water Harvesting on Micro-Nanotextured Biphilic Surfaces. **2022**. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnm.2c02439>.
- (2) Nioras, D.; Ellinas, K.; Constantoudis, V.; Gogolides, E. How Different Are Fog Collection and Dew Water Harvesting on Surfaces with Different Wetting Behaviors? *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2021**, *13* (40), 48322–48332. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsmi.1c16609>.
- (3) Tao, Y.; Wu, Q.; Huang, C.; Zhu, D.; Li, H. Electrically Heatable Carbon Scaffold Accommodated Monolithic Metal–Organic Frameworks for Energy-Efficient Atmospheric Water Harvesting. *Chem. Eng. J.* **2023**, *451*, 138547. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2022.138547>.
- (4) Lawson, K. W.; Lloyd, D. R. Membrane Distillation. *J. Membr. Sci.* **1997**, *124* (1), 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-011-4733-9>.
- (5) Warsinger, D. M.; Swaminathan, J.; Guillen-Burrieza, E.; Arafat, H. A.; Lienhard V, J. H. Scaling and Fouling in Membrane Distillation for Desalination Applications: A Review. *Desalination* **2015**, *356*, 294–313. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2014.06.031>.
- (6) Deng, L.; Li, P.; Liu, K.; Wang, X.; Hsiao, B. S. Robust Superhydrophobic Dual Layer Nanofibrous Composite Membranes with a Hierarchically Structured Amorphous Polypropylene Skin for Membrane Distillation. *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2019**, *7* (18), 11282–11297. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c9ta02662b>.
- (7) Horseman, T.; Yin, Y.; Christie, K. S.; Wang, Z.; Tong, T.; Lin, S. Wetting, Scaling, and Fouling in Membrane Distillation: State-of-the-Art Insights on Fundamental Mechanisms and Mitigation Strategies. *ACS ES&T Eng.* **2021**, *1* (1), 117–140. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsestengg.0c00025>.
- (8) Bogler, A.; Bar-Zeev, E. Membrane Distillation Biofouling: Impact of Feedwater Temperature on Biofilm Characteristics and Membrane Performance. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **2018**, *52* (17), 10019–10029. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.8b02744>.
- (9) Ferrando, D.; Toubiana, D.; Kandiyote, N. S.; Nguyen, T. H.; Nejidat, A.; Herzberg, M. Ambivalent Role of Calcium in the Viscoelastic Properties of Extracellular Polymeric Substances and the Consequent Fouling of Reverse Osmosis Membranes. *Desalination* **2018**, *429*, 12–19. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2017.12.006>.

- (10) Krivorot, M.; Kushmaro, A.; Oren, Y.; Gilron, J. Factors Affecting Biofilm Formation and Biofouling in Membrane Distillation of Seawater. *J. Memb. Sci.* **2011**, *376* (1), 15–24. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2011.01.061>.
- (11) Bogler, A.; Lin, S.; Bar-Zeev, E. Biofouling of Membrane Distillation, Forward Osmosis and Pressure Retarded Osmosis: Principles, Impacts and Future Directions. *J. Memb. Sci.* **2017**, *542*, 378–398. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2017.08.001>.
- (12) Xiao, Z.; Li, Z.; Guo, H.; Liu, Y.; Wang, Y.; Yin, H.; Li, X.; Song, J.; Nghiem, L. D.; He, T. Scaling Mitigation in Membrane Distillation: From Superhydrophobic to Slippery. *Desalination* **2019**, *466* (May), 36–43. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2019.05.006>.
- (13) Jia, W.; Kharraz, J. A.; Choi, P. J.; Guo, J.; Deka, B. J.; An, A. K. Superhydrophobic Membrane by Hierarchically Structured PDMS-POSS Electro spray Coating with Cauliflower-Shaped Beads for Enhanced MD Performance. *J. Memb. Sci.* **2020**, *597* (August 2019), 117638. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2019.117638>.
- (14) Warsinger, D. M.; Servi, A.; Van Belleghem, S.; Gonzalez, J.; Swaminathan, J.; Kharraz, J.; Chung, H. W.; Arafat, H. A.; Gleason, K. K.; Lienhard V, J. H. Combining Air Recharging and Membrane Superhydrophobicity for Fouling Prevention in Membrane Distillation. *J. Memb. Sci.* **2016**, *505*, 241–252. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2016.01.018>.
- (15) Kharraz, J. A.; An, A. K. Patterned Superhydrophobic Polyvinylidene Fluoride (PVDF) Membranes for Membrane Distillation: Enhanced Flux with Improved Fouling and Wetting Resistance. *J. Memb. Sci.* **2020**, *595*, 117596. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2019.117596>.
- (16) Shao, Y.; Han, M.; Wang, Y.; Li, G.; Xiao, W.; Li, X.; Wu, X.; Ruan, X.; Yan, X.; He, G.; Jiang, X. Superhydrophobic Polypropylene Membrane with Fabricated Antifouling Interface for Vacuum Membrane Distillation Treating High Concentration Sodium/Magnesium Saline Water. *J. Memb. Sci.* **2019**, *579* (February), 240–252. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2019.03.007>.
- (17) Liu, M.; Luo, Y.; Jia, D. Polydimethylsiloxane-Based Superhydrophobic Membranes: Fabrication, Durability, Repairability, and Applications. *Polym. Chem.* **2020**, *11* (13), 2370–2380. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c9py01861a>.
- (18) Ju, J.; Fejjari, K.; Cheng, Y.; Liu, M.; Li, Z.; Kang, W.; Liao, Y. Engineering Hierarchically Structured Superhydrophobic PTFE/POSS Nanofibrous Membranes for Membrane Distillation. *Desalination* **2020**, *486* (February), 114481. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2020.114481>.
- (19) Abdu, B.; Munirasu, S.; Kallem, P.; Hasan, S. W.; Banat, F. Investigating the Effect of Various Foulants on the Performance of Intrinsically Superhydrophobic Polyvinylidene Fluoride Membranes for Direct Contact Membrane Distillation. *Sep. Purif. Technol.* **2020**, *252* (April), 117416. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2020.117416>.
- (20) Nthunya, L. N.; Gutierrez, L.; Nxumalo, E. N.; Verliefde, A. R.; Mhlanga, S. D.;

- Onyango, M. S. F-MWCNTs/AgNPs-Coated Superhydrophobic PVDF Nanofibre Membrane for Organic, Colloidal, and Biofouling Mitigation in Direct Contact Membrane Distillation. *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* **2020**, *8* (2), 103654. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2020.103654>.
- (21) Sun, Q.; Yang, Z.; Hu, C.; Li, C.; Yan, G.; Wang, Z. Facile Preparation of Superhydrophobic PVDF Microporous Membranes with Excellent Anti-Fouling Ability for Vacuum Membrane Distillation. *J. Memb. Sci.* **2020**, *605* (March), 118106. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2020.118106>.
- (22) Li, Z.; Marlena, J.; Pranantyo, D.; Nguyen, B. L.; Yap, C. H. A Porous Superhydrophobic Surface with Active Air Plastron Control for Drag Reduction and Fluid Impalement Resistance †. **2019**, 16387–16396. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c9ta02745a>.
- (23) Zheng, L.; Wang, K.; Hou, D.; Jia, X.; Zhao, Z. Hierarchically-Structured Superhydrophobic POSS/PVDF Composite Membrane for Anti-Fouling and Anti-Wetting Membrane Distillation. *Desalination* **2022**, *526* (June 2021), 115512. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2021.115512>.
- (24) Li, Z.; Cheng, B.; Ju, J.; Kang, W.; Liu, Y. Development of a Novel Multi-Scale Structured Superhydrophobic Nanofiber Membrane with Enhanced Thermal Efficiency and High Flux for Membrane Distillation. *Desalination* **2021**, *501* (December 2020), 114834. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2020.114834>.
- (25) Lu, K. J.; Zhao, D.; Chen, Y.; Chang, J.; Chung, T. S. Rheologically Controlled Design of Nature-Inspired Superhydrophobic and Self-Cleaning Membranes for Clean Water Production. *npj Clean Water* **2020**, *3* (1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41545-020-0078-2>.
- (26) Su, C.; Horseman, T.; Cao, H.; Christie, K. S. S.; Li, Y.; Lin, S. Robust Superhydrophobic Membrane for Membrane Distillation with Excellent Scaling Resistance. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **2019**. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.9b04362>.
- (27) Hou, D.; Christie, K. S. S.; Wang, K.; Tang, M.; Wang, D.; Wang, J. Biomimetic Superhydrophobic Membrane for Membrane Distillation with Robust Wetting and Fouling Resistance. *J. Memb. Sci.* **2020**, *599*, 117708. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2019.117708>.
- (28) Liu, L.; Xiao, Z.; Liu, Y.; Li, X.; Yin, H.; Volkov, A.; He, T. Understanding the Fouling/Scaling Resistance of Superhydrophobic/Omniphobic Membranes in Membrane Distillation. *Desalination* **2021**, *499* (November 2020), 114864. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2020.114864>.
- (29) Zhu, Z.; Zhong, L.; Horseman, T.; Liu, Z.; Zeng, G.; Li, Z.; Lin, S.; Wang, W. Superhydrophobic-Omniphobic Membrane with Anti-Deformable Pores for Membrane Distillation with Excellent Wetting Resistance. *J. Memb. Sci.* **2021**, *620* (June), 118768. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2020.118768>.
- (30) Liao, Y.; Zheng, G.; Huang, J. J.; Tian, M.; Wang, R. Development of Robust and

- Superhydrophobic Membranes to Mitigate Membrane Scaling and Fouling in Membrane Distillation. *J. Memb. Sci.* **2020**, *601* (February), 117962. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2020.117962>.
- (31) Nthunya, L. N.; Gutierrez, L.; Khumalo, N.; Derese, S.; Mamba, B. B.; Verliefe, A. R.; Mhlanga, S. D. Superhydrophobic PVDF Nanofibre Membranes Coated with an Organic Fouling Resistant Hydrophilic Active Layer for Direct-Contact Membrane Distillation. *Colloids Surfaces A Physicochem. Eng. Asp.* **2019**, *575* (December 2018), 363–372. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colsurfa.2019.05.031>.
- (32) Zhang, Z.; Yang, W.; Gu, Z.; Huo, R. PVDF Films with Superhydrophobic Surface Fabricated by Plasma-Enhanced Chemical Vapor Deposition. *Adv. Mater. Res.* **2009**, *79–82*, 1451–1454. <https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMR.79-82.1451>.
- (33) Himma, N. F.; Prasetya, N.; Anisah, S.; Wenten, I. G. Superhydrophobic Membrane: Progress in Preparation and Its Separation Properties. *Rev. Chem. Eng.* **2018**, 1–28. <https://doi.org/10.1515/revce-2017-0030>.
- (34) Nthunya, L. N.; Gutierrez, L.; Lapeire, L.; Verbeken, K.; Zaouri, N.; Nxumalo, E. N.; Mamba, B. B.; Verliefe, A. R.; Mhlanga, S. D. Fouling-Resistant PVDF Nanofibre Membranes for the Desalination of Brackish Water in Membrane Distillation. *Sep. Purif. Technol.* **2019**, *228* (March), 115793. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2019.115793>.
- (35) Sinha Ray, S.; Dangayach, R.; Kwon, Y. N. Surface Engineering for Anti-Wetting and Antibacterial Membrane for Enhanced and Fouling Resistant Membrane Distillation Performance. *Chem. Eng. J.* **2021**, *405* (June 2020), 126702. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2020.126702>.
- (36) Yu, L.; Zhang, Y.; Zhang, B.; Liu, J.; Zhang, H.; Song, C. Preparation and Characterization of HPEI-GO/PES Ultrafiltration Membrane with Antifouling and Antibacterial Properties. *J. Memb. Sci.* **2013**, *447*, 452–462. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2013.07.042>.
- (37) Seo, D. H.; Pineda, S.; Woo, Y. C.; Xie, M.; Murdock, A. T.; Ang, E. Y. M.; Jiao, Y.; Park, M. J.; Lim, S. Il; Lawn, M.; Borghi, F. F.; Han, Z. J.; Gray, S.; Millar, G.; Du, A.; Shon, H. K.; Ng, T. Y.; Ostrikov, K. Anti-Fouling Graphene-Based Membranes for Effective Water Desalination. *Nat. Commun.* **2018**, *9* (1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-02871-3>.
- (38) You, Y. S.; Kang, S.; Mauchauffé, R.; Moon, S. Y. Rapid and Selective Surface Functionalization of the Membrane for High Efficiency Oil-Water Separation via an Atmospheric Pressure Plasma Process. *Sci. Rep.* **2017**, *7* (1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-15713-x>.
- (39) Yang, C.; Li, X. M.; Gilron, J.; Kong, D. feng; Yin, Y.; Oren, Y.; Linder, C.; He, T. CF₄ Plasma-Modified Superhydrophobic PVDF Membranes for Direct Contact Membrane Distillation. *J. Memb. Sci.* **2014**, *456*, 155–161. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2014.01.013>.

- (40) Yang, C.; Tian, M.; Xie, Y.; Li, X. M.; Zhao, B.; He, T.; Liu, J. *Effective Evaporation of CF₄ Plasma Modified PVDF Membranes in Direct Contact Membrane Distillation*; Elsevier, 2015; Vol. 482. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2015.01.059>.
- (41) Zhang, T.; Laborie, S.; Cabassud, C. Optical Method for in Operando Study of Membrane Distillation Wetting: Development for Desalination and Potential for Exploring Wetting Dynamics. *Desalination* **2022**, 539 (April). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2022.115944>.
- (42) Ricceri, F.; Blankert, B.; Ghaffour, N.; Vrouwenvelder, J. S.; Tiraferri, A.; Fortunato, L. Unraveling the Role of Feed Temperature and Cross-Flow Velocity on Organic Fouling in Membrane Distillation Using Response Surface Methodology. *Desalination* **2022**, 540 (May), 115971. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2022.115971>.
- (43) Ellinas, K.; Pujari, S. P.; Dragatogiannis, D. A.; Charitidis, C. A.; Tserepi, A.; Zuilhof, H.; Gogolides, E. Plasma Micro-Nanotextured , Scratch , Water and Hexadecane Resistant , Superhydrophobic , and Superamphiphobic Polymeric Surfaces with Per Fl Uorinated Monolayers. **2014**.
- (44) Ellinas, K.; Tserepi, A.; Gogolides, E. From Superamphiphobic to Amphiphilic Polymeric Surfaces with Ordered Hierarchical Roughness Fabricated with Colloidal Lithography and Plasma Nanotexturing. **2011**, 3960–3969. <https://doi.org/10.1021/la104481p>.
- (45) Zeniou, A.; Ellinas, K.; Olziersky, A.; Gogolides, E. Ultra-High Aspect Ratio Si Nanowires Fabricated with Plasma Etching: Plasma Processing, Mechanical Stability Analysis against Adhesion and Capillary Forces and Oleophobicity. *Nanotechnology* **2014**, 25 (3). <https://doi.org/10.1088/0957-4484/25/3/035302>.
- (46) Ellinas, K.; Kefallinou, D.; Stamatakis, K.; Gogolides, E.; Tserepi, A. Is There a Threshold in the Antibacterial Action of Superhydrophobic Surfaces? *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2017**, 9 (45), 39781–39789. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.7b11402>.
- (47) Smyrnakis, A.; Ioannou, D.; Ellinas, K.; Tserepi, A.; Gogolides, E. Real-Time Monitoring and Quantification of Underwater Superhydrophobicity. *Adv. Mater. Interfaces* **2022**, 9 (4), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1002/admi.202101393>.
- (48) Ioannou, D.; Hou, Y.; Shah, P.; Ellinas, K.; Kappl, M.; Sapalidis, A.; Constantoudis, V.; Butt, H.-J.; Gogolides, E. Plasma-Induced Superhydrophobicity as a Green Technology for Enhanced Air-Gap Membrane Distillation. *SSRN Electron. J.* **2022**. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4295130>.
- (49) Guo, J.; Deka, B. J.; Wong, P. W.; Sun, J.; An, A. K. Fabrication of Robust Green Superhydrophobic Hybrid Nanofiber-Nanosphere Membrane for Membrane Distillation. *Desalination* **2021**, 520, 115314. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2021.115314>.
- (50) Guo, J.; Deka, B. J.; Kim, K.-J.; An, A. K. Regeneration of Superhydrophobic TiO₂ Electrospun Membranes in Seawater Desalination by Water Flushing in Membrane Distillation. *Desalination* **2019**, 468, 114054. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2019.06.020>.

- (51) Pan, T.; Liu, J.; Deng, N.; Li, Z.; Wang, L.; Xia, Z.; Fan, J.; Liu, Y. ZnO Nanowires@PVDF Nanofiber Membrane with Superhydrophobicity for Enhanced Anti-Wetting and Anti-Scaling Properties in Membrane Distillation. *J. Memb. Sci.* **2021**, *621*, 118877. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2020.118877>.
- (52) Ellinas, K.; Tsougeni, K.; Petrou, P. S.; Boulousis, G.; Tsoukleris, D.; Pavlatou, E.; Tserepi, A.; Kakabakos, S. E.; Gogolides, E. Three-Dimensional Plasma Micro – Nanotextured Cyclo-Olefin-Polymer Surfaces for Biomolecule Immobilization and Environmentally Stable Superhydrophobic and Superoleophobic Behavior. *Chem. Eng. J.* **2016**, *300*, 394–403. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2016.04.137>.
- (53) Ellinas, K.; Tserepi, A.; Gogolides, E. Durable Superhydrophobic and Superamphiphobic Polymeric Surfaces and Their Applications: A Review. *Adv. Colloid Interface Sci.* **2017**, *250*, 132–157. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cis.2017.09.003>.
- (54) Tsougeni, K.; Vourdas, N.; Tserepi, A.; Gogolides, E.; Jean, M.; Imn, R.; Houssiniere, R. De. Mechanisms of Oxygen Plasma Nanotexturing of Organic Polymer Surfaces : From Stable Super Hydrophilic to Super Hydrophobic Surfaces. **2009**, *25* (19), 11748–11759. <https://doi.org/10.1021/la901072z>.
- (55) Zeniou, A.; Smyrnakis, A.; Constantoudis, V.; Awwsiuk, K.; Gogolides, E. One-Step Control of Hierarchy and Functionality of Polymeric Surfaces in a New Plasma Nanotechnology Reactor. *Nanotechnology* **2021**, *32* (23). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6528/abe6ca>.
- (56) Balis, E.; Sapalidis, A.; Pilatos, G.; Kouvelos, E.; Athanasekou, C.; Veziri, C.; Boutikos, P.; Beltsios, K. G.; Romanos, G. Enhancement of Vapor Flux and Salt Rejection Efficiency Induced by Low Cost-High Purity MWCNTs in Upscaled PVDF and PVDF-HFP Hollow Fiber Modules for Membrane Distillation. *Sep. Purif. Technol.* **2019**, *224* (June 2018), 163–179. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2019.04.067>.